

Fig. S3

Fig. S3. Morphometric PCA plot of 281 flowering plants in broad-ranging western sites for 10 informative flowering traits in paired analysis of *C. howellii* (purple triangles), putative *C. howellii* (downward lavender triangles), and *C. quamash* ssp. *breviflora* (blue circles). Traits in Appendix 2; species and site codes in Table 1, Fig. 2 map.